

AUTHENTIC MATERIALS AS A MEANS OF FORMING SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE

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Abstract. this article deals with the analysis of theoretical provisions determines the main role of authentic materials that contribute to the formation of socio-cultural competence of students.

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At this point in society's evolution, it is difficult to teach a foreign language without taking into account the globalization processes that have enveloped the whole community. It is critical to develop students' socio-cultural competency while teaching a foreign language - the capacity to employ information about the nation of the language being studied and its socio-cultural elements during communicating in a foreign language. The primary goal of secondary school foreign language instruction is to develop students' personalities so that they are capable and eager to participate in intercultural conversation in the target language, as well as to enhance their ability weave foreign language spoken activities. This goal is revealed in the unity of four interrelated components: educational, developmental, educational and practical. Among Russian scientists [E. M. Vereshchagin, V. G. Kostomarov, V. P. Furmanova, V. V. Vorobyov, Y. Prokhorov, V. V. Safonova, P. V. Sysoev, S. G. Ter-Minasova, G. V. Elizarova] in their writings, they emphasize the relevance of the socio-cultural component in the process of forming students' cross-cultural view of the world, deciding their place in a global world with a wide range of cultures. It is difficult to teach modern pupils a foreign language without socio-cultural knowledge about the target language nation, its people, manners, and customs, as well as other social phenomena.

Among the vast array of teaching materials and learning tools available in the modern teacher's arsenal, I would like to highlight authentic feature films as a complementary tool for the development of social competence and the ability to lead a discussion on a specific topic. The early twentieth century is defined by the overwhelming influence of visual media such as television, film, and the Internet. The younger generation understands visual information better than

any prior generation. O.V. Kochukova notes that “the use of feature films not only simulates the language situation and forms of speech competence of students, but in light of the latest approaches to the study of a foreign language helps to create the awareness and understanding of foreign culture and as a result it forms harmoniously developed personality in global intercultural space”. [1] L. G. Ionin says about the movie “as an important element of international information order”. [2]

Working with a video film in English instruction consists of three stages: pre-viewing, viewing, and post-viewing. A collection of assignments and exercises should be created at each step.

Work can be arranged as follows during the pre-watching stage: students can be asked a series of questions that generate a debate regarding the impending viewing. Following the hearing and discussion of the responses, the watching stage might be anticipated with brief information on the film's director, socio-cultural and historical viewpoint. It is critical to offer students with information before to seeing the film in order to enhance understanding of the film's purpose as well as a more accurate impression of the intricacies of the episodes. This should also be done in order to boost student motivation. Information might be offered in the form of recommendations, comments, and connections to more resources.

The screening stage comprises direct watching of the film or episode in English for the purpose of extracting various information: character descriptions, names of important places, storyline discussions, spotlight the Director's work, and the manner in general. Students are asked to undertake a variety of tasks while viewing, such as filling in the blanks, marking these characters, or building a series of episodes. These sorts of jobs require a combination of visual and aural awareness to get the best outcomes. At this point, students might distribute sheets containing the activities that they must complete during the preview and to aid them in the subsequent discussion.

We need to talk after seeing the first half of the movie. This form of work not only provides for the assessment of students' comprehension and perception of actual videodiscs, but it also serves as the foundation for a more in-depth analysis of the key characters and their interpersonal interactions.

Work on the movie discourse cannot be deemed complete until the study is limited to verbal methods rather than nonverbal. Because the film is presented nonverbally, you can use the variable when learning a new language.

It is best to base the post-viewing step of working with video discourse on a discussion of the students' responses. At this stage, the tasks are aimed at encouraging students to express their opinion about the fragment they saw, identifying and analyzing nonverbal means in the episode, interpreting the details of the film, comparing two eras, and identifying socio-cultural similarities and differences. You can finish the post-watching step by summarizing the viewing findings, having a final discussion, presenting creative ideas on the chosen topic based on new material, and having a discussion.

As a result, the usage of real movies is an excellent method of developing intercultural competency. A thorough study of movie discourse, both verbal and nonverbal implies familiarity with cultural, historical, and linguistic content. Students research the era, artists and authors do independent research, and produce a presentation on a topic speech in English.

Projects have a significant role in the school's instructional activities. Particularly intriguing projects for foreign language learners, because they produce a natural language environment and the necessity for linguistic contact. As demonstrated by worldwide experience and several studies, properly designed intentional collaboration of students on a project may provide better instructional benefits than mere communication. The project technique entails the broad use of problematic, research, and search methods, all with a clear focus on a real-world practical result that is important to the learner. The project approach allows information to be put into practice. Every foreign language instructor should be aware that in order to shape students' knowledge, skills, and abilities in one or more types of speaking activities, an installation is required for each student in the group. It is necessary to provide pupils the chance to solve any problem, to explore various solutions for them, so that children focus on the content of his comments to the center of attention were the thoughts and language, their formation. The instructor must not only be conversant with cross-cultural subjects, but also create methods to engage students in active cultural debate so that they understand the idiosyncrasies of the language to a new culture. The main task of the teacher is to shift the focus from various types of exercise to mental activity of students, and only the project method can help to solve this problem and turn the foreign language class into a discussion research club, where students must solve interesting problems based on their language training.

When implementing the project method, the instructor should take into account the stages of development of the project structure and its holding:

1. The teacher introduces a situation which allows identifying the problem (some problems) on the topics under discussion;
2. The teacher brainstorms where the hypotheses of the problem are discussed and justified each of them;
3. Discussion of test methods adopted by the hypothesis, possible sources of information to test a hypothesis, and presentation of results;
4. Work in groups to find facts and arguments to support or refute a hypothesis
5. Protection of the projects of each of the groups with opposition from all those present.

The most significant aspect of project methodology is to create an issue that students will work on while working on the project's theme. The instructor must consider what type of assistance may be supplied to children without providing a ready-made answer. It is best to plan a series of projects for which the project technique is suggested. At all phases of project work, the teacher should keep track of each student's activity. To that goal, the instructor should employ self- and mutual control. Students might begin by submitting a rough copy of the project to the teacher. You can ask two instructors to act as experts in lesson protection initiatives.

All of the greatest concepts from old and current techniques of teaching foreign languages were utilized in the design approach. Today's school report ready information, memorization, and awareness of other people's opinions - may all be considered forms of learning.

The approach of teaching a foreign language places a high value on the issue of text authenticity. Because the purpose of teaching a foreign language is to develop students' capacity to utilize the target language as a tool of genuine communication in cross-cultural discussion, the material on which learning takes place should be authentic. The linguistic element of authentic literature is distinguished by significant originality and diversity of language. They are densely packed with pronouns, particles, interjections, words with emotional undertones, phrases designed to elicit associative links, phraseological units, idioms, and speech clichés. Sentences can be kept short and non-expanded; understatement is also an option. Authentic texts can be changed, but not at the expense of their authenticity. There are several sorts of texts available, all of which are cognitively important and accurately represent the idiosyncrasies of everyday life, life, and culture in the language being studied. Texts of this type include pragmatic, grocery list, TV program, and recipes.

Epistolary – personal, business letters, cards, etc.

Articles from newspapers and journals, as well as excerpts from imaginative literature such as poetry, novels, essays, cartoons, and so on. All sorts of writings deal with potential concerns and acceptable solutions.

The lesson is built around the texts; they send a decisive impulse or provide tasks, important information, and may provoke students to an exciting discussion; they supplement and expand the teacher's speech; and they contribute to the development of students' independent activity (for example, they are given a task to make a list of keywords on a topic using the text they read). Working with text in a foreign language class might vary based on the teacher's aims and objectives, as well as the students' degree of foreign language competency. However, the instructor should not lose sight of the fundamental aim, which is to develop communicative competence, or to learn to converse in a foreign language, and in this case, the best material for this reason can serve as the text's content. It is obvious that the selection of authentic texts is the responsibility of the instructor, who can obtain your text from a variety of sources, including the Internet, while keeping the educational process's criteria in mind.

We propose a variety of challenges for working with text that will aid in the development of communicative competence of its components (language, speech, socio-cultural, compensatory competence) and transform this work into a fascinating process of textual information processing and comprehension.

1. The framing of the textual questions. Your questions should be directed at all participants. The student defines your question after answering the query text. Only if students grasp the content will they be able to correctly answer questions.

2. Abstracting (compressing) the entire text or portions of it. Exchange students who have written the text concisely and answered the following questions from the teachers: "If you didn't read the text, you could guess what was going on?" Why (or why not)? What may I exclude from this citation? "What is crucial?" After responding (in writing) to the questions posed, the texts are returned to their authors.

3. Anticipation of the text's next steps. Students are instructed to fold a piece of paper into two columns: "information" on the left and "forecast" on the right. When they receive the title of the piece, they write it in the left column, while they write their assumptions and explain them in the right column. Here, I'd want to underline the need of practicing predicting skills using information

from a previously read section of the book. The instructor can cut off a section of the text and assign pupils assignments to complete the table. On the board, interesting hypotheses can be written. This strategy appeals to students' knowledge, experience, viewpoint, and creativity.

4. Text segmentation into semantic paragraphs. Simultaneously, students must discuss why they split the material into sections and how paragraphs differ.

5. Creating visuals in the text if there are a few themes for discussion or a lot of information. The chart may resemble a tree: the roots represent the students' understanding of the subject, the trunk represents the title of the text, the branches represent the key categories of information, and the foliage represents facts for each topic of the book. Students may draw an image of your tree, either in groups or individually, and then remark on their work.

6. Association of the text's "voice" after reading the genuine text, students express their thoughts on what they read by envisioning who and how this narrative may be told.

7. After reading, do a written assignment. This might include, for example, writing a journal on behalf of the story's hero, creating an advertising, or creating a tour guide for a traveler.

As a result, we can draw the following conclusions. Reading authentic texts is a cognitive activity that manifests itself in creative and design jobs, job preparation questions, matching, known and unknown, communicating with previously known facts, plot prediction, the structuring of semantic relations in the text, enriching the experience by reading different texts on the same subject, and so on. It is necessary to diversify tasks when reading the text since pupils' enthusiasm and interest in reading declines when completing routine chores. E. I. Passov claims that "reading is itself a communion of the mediated book". [3]

List of used literature:

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